

U. S. NAVY'S DEEP SUBMERGENCE FORCES

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ABSTRACT

Since its inception in 1970, Submarine Development Group ONE has functioned as the U. S. Navy's sole operating arm for underwater search, recovery, and rescue. As such, it maintains the largest, most diverse collection of Deep Submergence assets in the world, including submarines, manned and unmanned submersibles, search systems, diving systems, surface ships, and shore facilities. A wealth of operational experiences have been acquired with these assets over the past thirteen years in both Atlantic and Pacific Oceans, leading to the establishment of numerous techniques and equipment developments. This paper will describe specific Submarine Development Group systems and present results of several recent operations. Future plans will also be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The U. S. Navy's operational command for deep submergence systems is Submarine Development Group ONE located in San Diego, California. The Development Group was established in 1967 by the Chief of Naval Operations as part of the Pacific Submarine Force. It acts as the Navy's sole operating arm devoted to the development of deep submergence capabilities for search, location, recovery, and rescue anywhere in the world's oceans.

Establishment of the Development Group was an outgrowth of the Deep Submergence Systems Review Group established by the Secretary of the Navy in 1963 after the loss of the Submarine THRESHER and the demonstrated inadequacy of the Navy's deep ocean capabilities as revealed in the searches for the THRESHER in 1963 and 1964 and the H-Bomb off Palomares, Spain in 1966. Prior to 1967, deep ocean capabilities, where they existed at all, rested almost entirely in various prototype and "one-of-a-kind" systems. These were commonly operated by numerous organizations such as Navy laboratories, universities, and other institutions generally supported by research and development funds. Historically, the operating forces of the Navy (i.e., Fleet) were forced to rely on this mixture of deep ocean assets to respond to contingency operations.

In the ten years since its inception, however, the Development Group has centralized the Navy's deep submergence operational experience and assembled the largest array of diverse deep ocean assets ever operated and maintained under one organization, civilian or military. These assets include deep submergence vehicles, deep submergence rescue vehicles, support ships, a deep diving research submarine, submarine rescue ships, advanced saturation diving systems, schools for training divers and deep submergence vehicles operators, shore-based maintenance activities,

and a biomedical research department. The greatest wealth of experience to date, however, has been with deep submergence vehicles. Hence, this paper will be directed toward recent experiences with these systems.

DEEP SUBMERGENCE RESCUE

The Deep Submergence Rescue Vehicle (DSRV) system has been designed to provide a quick-reaction, world-wide capability to rescue personnel from a disabled submarine, lying on the ocean floor at less than collapse depth.

Each of the Navy's two DSRV's (MYSTIC and AVALON) are designed to mate over the hatch of a disabled submarine and, with a crew of three, carry up to 24 rescuees per trip back to safety. The outer hull, made of fiberglass reinforced plastic, is 50 feet in length and 8 feet in diameter. Within the lightweight outer hull are three interconnected spheres, each 1½ meters in outside diameter and made of HY-140 steel. Each vehicle has an air weight of 75,000 lbs and is capable of submerging to a depth of 5,000 feet.

Propulsion and maneuvering of the DSRV is achieved by an electrically-powered stern propeller within a moveable control shroud and four electrically-powered ducted thrusters (two horizontal and two vertical). The DSRV is designed to hover in currents up to one knot and mate with a disabled submarine lying on the ocean floor at angles up to 45 degrees. Each vehicle has a submerged endurance of approximately eight hours.

Special sensors and equipment necessary for navigation, location and safety include a horizontal obstacle avoidance sonar, vertical obstacle avoidance sonar, altitude/depth sonar, and short range sonar which outlines any object directly beneath the DSRV mating skirt and assists in determining the orientation of the disabled submarine. In addition, each DSRV has a doppler sonar, transponder interrogation sonar, television and 35mm still cameras, external flood lights, and viewports in the forward and middle spheres.

MYSTIC

Located at the Submarine Rescue Unit at North Island Naval Air Station, San Diego, California, each DSRV and its associated support equipment is capable of being air transported by three Air Force C-141A aircraft. At-sea support is to be provided either by a new catamaran ASR-21 Class Submarine Rescue Ship or an SSN-637 Class nuclear attack submarine modified to serve as a Mother Submarine, capable of transporting, replenishing, launching, and recovering the DSRV while submerged.

During 1982, MYSTIC conducted two operations of note. The first, taking place during August, was an Alternate Mission Exercise involving equipment and procedures not normally used in the rescue scenario; rather, these operations capitalized on the usefulness of the DSRV as a search/work platform. The Alternate Mission Package consists of a dual range sidescan sonar, binocular optics, two television monitors, video tape recorder, and 16mm picture camera.

During the August time frame, MYSTIC was tasked to search for and identify various objects such as a submarine anchor and deep seat training fixture. The boat successfully operated in a beacon field and exercised all system components in consort with standard onboard functions. These operations provided valuable training which will be applied toward future problems such as torpedo and aircraft recovery.

During the period 6-22 December 1982, the MYSTIC participated in a flyaway exercise to Charleston, South Carolina. This exercise was both for training and for the certification of the twin-hulled ASR, USS ORTOLAN, for launch, recovery, and tracking of the DSRV.

The DSRV system was loaded aboard two C-141s and one C-5A (figure 1) for the flight from North Island Naval Air Station in San Diego, homeport for the DSRV's.

Figure 1. DSRV-1 MYSTIC being loaded into C-5A for flyaway exercise to Charleston, South Carolina.

Once at Charleston, the system was highway transported to the naval base on its own trailers. The MYSTIC was fit up on the submarine, USS SEAHORSE (SSN-669), which was to act as a mother submarine (MOSUB) for recovery backup and also as a training aid for docking and seating. The MYSTIC was then installed on USS ORTOLAN (figure 2) and transported to a dive site south of Grand Bahama Island. Two dives, numbers 411 and 412, were conducted in this area with successful launches and recoveries using the center well-lowered cradle of ORTOLAN and several locations and landings on the submerged SEAHORSE. Following this exercise, the system was taken back to base and offloaded for transport to Charleston Air Force Base and the subsequent flight home. Not only was this an effective training and certification evaluation, it also gave additional credibility to the practice of quickly transporting a complex system several thousand miles away and having it perform reliably at its destination.

Figure 2. MYSTIC being positioned on center well cradle of ASR-22 ORTOLAN.

DOLPHIN

USS DOLPHIN (AGSS-555) is the Navy's deep diving submarine. The ship conducts weapons, acoustic, environmental, marine engineering, and tactical operations in support of the Navy's research and development communities. Manned by a crew of three officers and twenty-six enlisted men, DOLPHIN is capable of carrying over twelve tons of scientific equipment to sea for periods as long as three weeks. The ship can deploy from her San Diego, California homeport for out-of-area operations extending up to several months.

In April 1982, the ship conducted two weeks of highly productive upper ocean turbulence experiments to examine near-surface seawater mixing off the coast of Southern California. The ship carried an instrument cluster mounted on a nine thousand pound tripod mounted on the forward deck (figure 3). Half of these operations were conducted in consort with the R/V ACANIA. The operation was sponsored by the Naval Postgraduate School at Monterey, California and the University of British Columbia in Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada.

Figure 3. USS DOLPHIN shown with turbulence probe tripod mounted on bow.

During February 1983, the ship conducted a ten day "Deep Tow Sonar Array" operation in support of on-going research sponsored by the Naval Ocean Systems Center, San Diego, California. In this operation, a

four thousand foot passive sonar array was towed by a six thousand foot coaxial tow cable. The tow cable length was adjusted by means of a 12,000 lb. hydraulically-driven winch mounted externally on the ship's forward deck. This operation satisfactorily demonstrated the Deep Tow System and helped to establish the baseline operation of the steerable beam, acoustic signal processing system for passive ranging.

In April 1983, DOLPHIN tested a newly designed deployment towing system that offers an inexpensive and practical way to move the ship long distances at relatively high speeds. The "demonstration tow" utilized USS POINT LOMA (AGDS-2) as the towing vessel. DOLPHIN was towed five hundred nautical miles during a four day period at speeds of up to ten knots. Higher speeds are anticipated for future transits.

During June 1983, DOLPHIN conducted four days of operations on the 3-Dimensional Tracking Range Facility at San Clemente Island near Southern California. The test evaluated the ability to safely control a submerged submarine in three dimensions on the range. Submarine tracking certification requirements included exercising automatic tracking alarm features which can alert the submarine to avoid collisions with other vessels on the range and to prevent grounding when approaching shallow waters.

SEA CLIFF

SEA CLIFF (figure 4) a small, three-man submersible with an operating depth of 6,500 feet, is used for underwater research, exploration, and work. Its 7 ft HY-100 pressure hull is cradled within an aluminum framework and the entire assembly is covered with a free-flooding GRP skin. The vehicle is 26 feet long, 12 feet wide, and 13 feet high and weighs approximately 25 tons. It is equipped with two 7-function manipulators which can grasp or cut cable.

Figure 4. DSV-4 SEA CLIFF as a 6,500 ft depth work submersible.

During February 1982, SEA CLIFF conducted extensive surveys of the ocean bottom west of San Clemente Island. The survey established the nature of conditions for a future tracking range. In addition, the vehicle was used to recover and survey hydrophones on an existing 3-D range and verify range tracking accuracy. This latter service was not originally planned, but the need was recognized after operations began. The support ship, TRANSQUEST, and SEA CLIFF were tracked by range supplied equipment throughout the mission. The following results were obtained: the 3D range is able to track targets much further

away from SCI than previously thought; the range was able to accurately direct SEA CLIFF to a hydrophone location, thus verifying range accuracy for a submerged target; constant depth comparisons with SEA CLIFF depth sensors versus range computed depth provided a basis for range depth accuracy. This was the first opportunity for the range to track a submerged target from the surface to the ocean floor and exercise this area of the computer programs. The tracking results obtained when SEA CLIFF was deeper than the bottom plane of the range were discarded by range personnel until analysis proved them correct. The reversal of signs when a target is below the range had not been previously observed and aided in "Z" axis verification.

In February 1983, the SEA CLIFF was used to attempt recovery of a World War II Douglas Dauntless dive bomber (SBD-3), ditched in 1942 and resting in 3900 feet of water, 15 nautical miles off San Diego (figure 5). The plane had been located on a routine training mission 24 months previously and was considered to be in good condition and of significant historical value. The operation called for SEA CLIFF to attach a 5/8 inch Kevlar line to a lift strap, originally installed over the cockpit, and transfer the line to the twin hull ASR, USS PIGEON for recovery.

Figure 5. WW II dive bomber prior to attempted recovery. Line in foreground is attached to aircraft lift strap and is being payed out from reel on SEA CLIFF.

Unfortunately, the lift structure parted during the lift when the plane was 1500 feet off the bottom. The SBD-3 sailed back down, stuck in the mud, nose down, and gradually layed over upside down (figure 6). Another dive by SEA CLIFF verified the bomber's position and established that its condition was still good, setting the stage for another attempt at recovery, possibly during the summer of 1983.

Figure 6. Dive bomber in nose down attitude immediately following fall back to bottom. Currents later pushed it over on its back.

TURTLE

The DSV TURTLE has basically identical characteristics to SEA CLIFF, except it has been tested and certified to a depth of 10,000 feet.

During October 1982, TURTLE was instrumental in the recovery of a massive OTEC cold water pipe (CWP), moored in 4,500 feet of water off the island of Hawaii. The CWP was used to test the feasibility of pumping cold water from depth to condense refrigerant gas, vaporized by the relatively warm surface water during the OTEC process. The pipe actually consisted of a bundle of three 4-foot diameter polyethylene pipes 2250 feet long which were moored 1,000 feet below the surface (figure 7) and abandoned. A critical part of the salvage effort was assigned to the TURTLE, specifically to cut the CWP bottom anchor chain so that the pipe bundle could float free for tow back to port. Initial dives on the site provided an adequate survey. Then the submersible attached pyronol torches to the chain, which were fired remotely after TURTLE cleared the area. The torches were unsuccessful in cutting through the chain, so yet another dive was conducted to mechanically cut the 1 3/8 inch wire ropes that held the pipe to the anchor chain. This was successful and the CWP was recovered.

Figure 7. Arrangement of OTEC Cold Water Pipe (CWP) prior to recovery.

STSS

The Surface Towed Search System (STSS) consists of a sensor vehicle (figure 8), a handling/overboarding unit, a traction winch and cable storage reel, and topside control center. The vehicle is designed for 20,000 ft. operations and carries a high quality 2-beam, side looking CTFM sonar, and high capacity (5,600 exposures) photo camera. The vehicle is picked up from a deck transfer track, rotated 90 degrees, and plunged beneath the water surface by the stern-mounted handling crane. It is then streamed out and towed from the boom tip which also serves as the submerged tow point. Displays and controls are all located within the operations vans including winch controls which regulate fish height above the bottom as it flies at typical speeds of 1-2 knots.

Figure 8. Surface Towed Search System (STSS) vehicle during launch. Overboarding A-Frame also functions as submerged tow point.

In November 1982, the STSS, still undergoing fleet acceptance testing, conducted search operations for a sunken submarine off the coast of San Diego in 4,000 feet of water. A deep ocean transponder (DOT) field was sown and a systematic sonar search conducted, resulting in the location and inspection of the SABALO (figure 9) with TV and photo camera. Excellent video resolution was obtained at altitudes from 40 feet down to 5 feet from object of interest. All in all, some 150 hours of tow time were accumulated in 1982, bringing the STSS closer to serving as an operational fleet system.

Figure 9. Photo of USS SABALO stern taken by STSS during testing.

FUTURE PLANS

The nature of deep submergence operations will continue much as it has. However, the effectiveness of those operations should increase with increased reliability of existing assets and the addition/improvement of others.

The SEA CLIFF has been dismantled and certain components sent to Mare Island Naval Shipyard, where a conversion to 20,000 feet operation is being conducted (figure 10). Current plans call for completion of the conversion in late 1983.

Figure 10. Titanium pressure hull for 20,000 ft. SEA CLIFF conversion being machined at Mare Island Naval Shipyard.

The STSS will be upgraded and made more transportable by the addition of a Unitized Loading System (ULS) which places most major system components on a single bed (figure 11) which can be highway or air transported and tied down to the deck of a selected ship of opportunity such as a T-ATF.

Figure 11. Arrangement of proposed Unitized Loading System (ULS) for STSS.

Acquisition of a commercial medium-depth ROV will take place in fiscal year 1984 with another scheduled for fiscal year 1985. This will expand the role and capability of the Unmanned Vehicle Detachment and provide assets which have not been readily available up until now for performing long-term remote work functions.

The continual accumulation of experience within the Navy, coupled with a conscious program for improvement of systems can only result in a more powerful role for the navy deep submergence program in the future.